

Single-Layer Versus Double-Layer Ileocolic Anastomosis in Right Hemicolectomy: A Randomized Controlled Trial

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ABSTRACT

ARTICLE DETAILS

Background: Gastrointestinal surgery frequently necessitates bowel anastomosis, and the choice of technique significantly influences postoperative outcomes. Since Travers, Lembert, and Halsted established the early principles of intestinal suturing, anastomosis has emerged as a fundamental component of gastrointestinal surgery. To ensure anastomotic integrity and optimal patient recovery, meticulous surgical technique, precise tissue apposition, and gentle tissue handling are crucial. Both single-layer and double-layer anastomotic techniques are widely used, but there is ongoing debate about their comparative safety, efficiency, and effectiveness.

Objective: To evaluate and compare operative time, postoperative complications, hospital stay, and short-term mortality between single-layer and double-layer ileocolic anastomoses in patients undergoing right hemicolectomy.

Method: This is a single-center prospective hospital-based interventional double-blinded randomized controlled trial that included 46 patients undergoing right hemicolectomy at No. (1) Military Hospital (700 bedded) from 01/12/2022 to 31/05/2024 (total of 18 months). The patients were randomized into group A (single-layer anastomosis, n = 23) and group B (double-layer anastomosis, n = 23) using block randomization. Operative times, postoperative complications (anastomotic leak, surgical site infection), length of hospital stay, and 30-day mortality were recorded. Data was analyzed using Student's t-test, with p<0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results: Among a total of 46 patients, 54.3% were male patients and 45.6% were female patients. Most patients in both groups were aged 41–60 years, while the fewest patients in Group A were over 80 years and in Group B were between 61 and 80 years. The mean operative time was significantly shorter in Group A (18.43 ± 2.68 minutes) compared to Group B (28.70 ± 2.55 minutes, p<0.001). Disease profiles included carcinoma, tuberculosis, and perforation. Both groups demonstrated high success rates with comparable complication profiles. Anastomotic leaks occurred in 4% of Group A and 9% of Group B (NS). Surgical site infection was seen in 9% of both groups. There was no 30-day mortality. The mean duration of the postoperative hospital stay was 7.39 ± 0.50 days in group A and 7.61 ± 0.50 days in group B (p = 0.14).

Conclusion: Both single-layer and double-layer anastomosis techniques are effective and safe for right hemicolectomy. The single-layer technique offers a significant reduction in operative time without increasing postoperative complications, suggesting it as a time-efficient alternative for bowel anastomosis.

KEYWORDS: Ileocolic anastomosis, right hemicolectomy, single-layer, double-layer, randomized controlled trial, surgical outcomes, operation time, hospital stay.

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INTRODUCTION

Anastomotic integrity is one of the most critical determinants of early postoperative outcomes in gastrointestinal surgery. The technique used for anastomosis plays a pivotal role in the healing process. Hand-sewn intestinal anastomosis remains the most performed method worldwide due to the availability of suture materials, affordability, and the widespread familiarity of surgeons with the procedure. Anastomoses may be fashioned using either a double-layer or a single-layer suturing technique. The primary aim of an anastomosis is to achieve secure bowel alignment that restores intestinal continuity and allows early passage of contents (1).

Right hemicolectomy is commonly performed for a range of pathologies, including bowel obstruction, incarcerated hernia, tuberculosis, and both benign and malignant tumors. In these patients, anastomotic leak can have devastating consequences, including peritonitis, abscess, fistula formation, multiorgan failure, reoperation, and death. Thus, an optimal anastomotic technique is of paramount importance (2).

Traditionally, bowel anastomosis has been performed using a double-layer technique, first described by Senn in 1893. By 1931, more than 50 different techniques for gastrointestinal anastomosis had been reported. The single-layer continuous anastomosis, first described by Hautefeuille in 1976 and later mentioned by Allen et al. in the United States, has since emerged as a popular alternative method (3).

Bowel anastomoses may be fashioned as end-to-end, side-to-side, or end-to-side, depending on the indication and surgeon preference. Techniques for creating anastomosis include single- and double-layer hand-sewn methods, stapled anastomosis, and more recently, adjuncts such as tissue adhesives and laser welding. Studies by Muhammad Jawaid Rajput and Abdul Sattar Memon demonstrated that end-to-end single-layer extramucosal interrupted anastomosis using polyglactin is a safe and effective technique. Similarly, Askarpour and Sarmast (2005–2006) reported that single and double-layer techniques had comparable complication rates, with single-layer closure offering the added advantages of shorter operative time and reduced cost (4).

Currently, single-layer extramucosal anastomosis is widely favored, as advocated by Norman Matheson of Aberdeen, because it likely causes the least tissue necrosis and luminal narrowing. Multiple trials and clinical studies have confirmed that single-layer anastomoses are faster to construct and comparable in strength to double-layer anastomoses (5).

Despite these advantages, concerns remain regarding the single-layer continuous technique, particularly the theoretical risk of stricture formation due to a purse-string effect when non-absorbable sutures are used. However,

evidence suggests that the technique is not associated with an increased risk of leaks or strictures. On the other hand, double-layer closure has been linked to devascularization, focal necrosis, infection, and increased risk of tissue strangulation due to uneven suture tension (6).

Several studies have shown that the single-layer technique does not carry an increased risk of anastomotic leakage or stricture formation. Leakage remains one of the most feared complications of bowel surgery, with a reported incidence of 1.3–7.7%. It is associated with significant morbidity, prolonged hospital stays, increased cost, and, in severe cases, mortality, reoperation, or multiorgan failure (7).

The conventional double-layer anastomosis, which typically uses absorbable sutures for the inner layer and non-absorbable sutures for the outer layer, is time-consuming, technically demanding, and carries a risk of mucosal strangulation and submucosal vascular plexus damage, potentially predisposing to bowel ischemia, necrosis, and stricture (8).

In contrast, the single-layer extramucosal technique approximates only the seromuscular layer, incorporates the submucosa—the strongest layer of the gut wall—preserves the submucosal vascular plexus, and maintains anatomy, thereby reducing the risk of necrosis and stricture formation. A Cochrane review concluded that single-layer anastomosis can be performed more quickly and is comparable to double-layer closure in terms of anastomotic leak, perioperative complications, mortality, and hospital stay (9). Despite this evidence, the single-layer technique is not yet universally adopted, and there is limited data from South Asian populations, where practice patterns and patient factors may differ. This lack of regional evidence may partly explain the slow uptake of this technique in our surgical setting.

Therefore, this randomized controlled trial aims to compare single-layer and double-layer intestinal anastomosis following right hemicolectomy. Outcomes were assessed in terms of anastomotic leak, postoperative morbidity, 30-day mortality, and length of hospital stay. The results of this study aim to contribute valuable evidence regarding the safety, efficacy, and feasibility of single-layer closure compared to the conventional double-layer technique in our surgical setting. Establishing robust local evidence could encourage wider adoption of the more efficient and tissue-sparing single-layer technique and potentially improve patient outcomes.

Our hypothesis was that single-layer ileocolic anastomosis is as safe and effective as double-layer ileocolic anastomosis in right hemicolectomy.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

This is a single-center hospital-based interventional double-blinded randomized controlled trial. This trial was conducted in the surgical unit of No. (1) Military Hospital

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(700 bedded) in Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar. This trial was carried out over 18 months following approval by the institutional ethical review board. The recruitment start date was 01/12/2022, and the end date was 31/05/2024. A total of 46 adult patients (>18 years) undergoing elective right hemicolectomy for benign or malignant disease were enrolled after written informed consent. Patients with traumatic perforation, existing colonic stump leakage, or wound complications beyond 30 days were excluded.

Patients were evaluated using a detailed history, a thorough physical examination, and investigations such as liver function tests, a complete blood picture, urea, creatinine, viral serology, abdominal ultrasound, and CT. Informed written consent explaining the research procedure was obtained before surgery. The required sample size for each group was 46, for a total of 23. A total of 46 patients were randomly allocated to group A (single-layer) (n = 23) and group B (double-layer) (n = 23) by the block randomization method (Figure 1).

Figure 1. CONSORT Flow Diagram

For a total sample size of 46 patients, there were 5 blocks, each with 10 patients. In each block of 10 cases, two methods were allocated in random order. A random block design was generated by using Graphpad Prism Software. The first case was allocated to one block using the envelope method. Then, the next 9 cases were sequentially placed in the same block. After completing one block, the same procedure was done for another block of 10 patients. A system of sequentially numbered, sealed, opaque envelopes containing treatment methods was used. The envelopes were opened in the operating theatre just before the operation. By

using this randomization method, all patients were divided into two equal groups throughout the whole study period.

Patients underwent preoperative assessment by a consultant anesthesiologist, and all operations were performed in the same theatre under general anesthesia. Fasting for 6 hours was required, and prophylactic antibiotics were administered at induction of anesthesia. The abdomen was cleaned and draped sterilely.

Operative Procedure

All patients underwent a standard right hemicolectomy through a midline incision under general anesthesia, following adequate preoperative optimization and strict aseptic precautions.

Single-Layer Ileocolic Anastomosis

For Group A, single-layer continuous end-to-end ileocolic anastomosis was constructed with 2-0 Vicryl® sutures, incorporating all layers except mucosa. Each stitch was 4–6 mm from the cut edge, with 5 mm spacing between stitches. Special care was taken at the mesenteric border with slightly larger bites to ensure adequate seal. Mesenteric defects were approximated to avoid internal herniation. The anastomosis was gently palpated between fingers to confirm luminal patency.

Figure 2. Dissection of caecal tumour for right hemicolectomy (Group A).

Figure 3. Single-layer continuous ileocolic end-to-end anastomosis with 2-0 Vicryl® suture (Group A).

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Figure 4. Resection of transverse colon and terminal ileum for right hemicolectomy (Group A).

Figure 7. Double-layer ileocolic end-to-end anastomosis following right hemicolectomy (Group B).

Figure 5. Single-layer continuous ileocolic end-to-end anastomosis with 2-0 Vicryl® suture (Group A).

Figure 8. Resection of transverse colon and terminal ileum for right hemicolectomy (Group B).

Double-Layer Ileocolic Anastomosis

In Group B, double-layer end-to-end ileocolic anastomosis was fashioned with an inner continuous transmural layer using 2-0 Vicryl® and an outer seromuscular interrupted Lembert layer using 2-0 silk, inverting the inner layer.

Figure 6. Operative view after resection of transverse colon and terminal ileum (Group B).

Figure 9. Double-layer ileocolic end-to-end anastomosis with inner continuous 2-0 Vicryl® sutures and outer interrupted 2-0 silk sutures (Group B).

Mesenteric defects were approximated to avoid internal herniation. The anastomosis was gently palpated between fingers to confirm luminal patency.

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Figure 10. Approximation of mesenteric defect after ileocolic end-to-end anastomosis (both groups).

Abdominal drains were placed in the hepatorenal pouch and pelvic cavity. The midline laparotomy incision was closed at the fascial level by mass closure with non-absorbable sutures, and the skin incision was closed using interrupted non-absorbable sutures.

After surgery, antibiotics were administered. Postoperative pain control was achieved with intravenous tramadol 1mg/kg, with daily doses up to 72 hours. Postoperative monitoring included daily clinical assessment for anastomotic leaks, surgical site infections, and other complications. Suspected anastomotic leaks were confirmed using clinical findings and abdominal ultrasonography during the postoperative period. Thereafter, postoperative outcomes of both group A and group B were evaluated and compared. Then if the patients had no postoperative complications within two weeks, they were discharged from the hospital. Patients were followed up for 30 days postoperatively, and outcomes were recorded in a structured proforma. Statistical analysis was performed by using the SPSS® Statistic software package version 28.0, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Figure 11. Resected right-sided colonic specimens with tumours (red arrows) following right hemicolectomy (Group A).

Figure 12. Resected right-sided colonic specimens following right hemicolectomy (Group B): tumor (A, red arrow) and caecal perforation (B, yellow arrow).

This clinical trial reviewed and compared the age and sex distribution, disease groups of patients undergoing right hemicolectomy, duration of single-layer and double-layer anastomosis, postoperative outcomes (including anastomotic leak, surgical site infection, and 30-day mortality), and the duration of postoperative hospital stay for both groups.

Statistical analysis

Statistics were analyzed on a total of 46 patients using SPSS® Statistics version 28.0. The categorical data was calculated by the statistical method chi-square. For continuous variables, the statistical significance of patients was analyzed by two independent Student's t-tests.

RESULTS

In this study, patients were divided into two groups: Group A (single-layer) and Group B (double-layer). In Group A, the majority of patients were between 41 and 60 years of age (12 patients, 52%), while the smallest proportion belonged to the >80 years age group (1 patient, 4%). In Group B, most patients were also in the 41–60 years age group (11 patients, 50%), whereas the fewest were in the 61–80 years age group.

Table 1. Age distribution in both groups

Age Group	Group A (Single-layer)	Group B (Double-layer)	Total
18-40	8 (34.7%)	9 (39.1%)	17 (36.9%)
41-60	12 (52.1%)	11 (47.8%)	23 (50%)
61-80	2 (8.6%)	3 (13%)	5 (10.8%)
>80	1 (4.3%)	0	1 (2.1%)

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Figure 13. Age distribution in both study groups

In conclusion, the age distribution demonstrated that most patients in both groups were between 41 and 60 years, whereas the smallest proportion were aged above 80 years.

Table 2. Sex distribution in both groups

Sex	Group A (Single-layer)	Group B (Double-layer)	Total
Male	13 (56.5%)	12 (52.1%)	25 (54.3%)
Female	10 (43.4%)	11 (47.8%)	21 (45.6%)

Figure 14. Sex distribution in both study groups

The sex distribution showed a male predominance in both groups. Group A (single-layer) included 13 males (57%) and 10 females (43%), while Group B (double-layer) comprised 12 males (52%) and 11 females (48%). Overall, 25 males and 21 females underwent right hemicolectomy, confirming a slightly higher proportion of male patients.

Table 3. Disease groups of patients undergoing right hemicolectomy

Disease Group	Group A (Single-layer)	Group B (Double-layer)	Total
Caecal TB	3	3	6 (13%)
Carcinoma ascending colon	6	5	11 (23.9%)

Carcinoma caecum	2	5	7 (15.2%)
Caecal perforation	4	4	8 (17.3%)
Carcinoma of hepatic flexure	6	4	10 (21.7%)
Others	2	2	4 (8.6%)

Figure 15. Disease groups of patients undergoing right hemicolectomy

This study included a total of 46 patients, equally divided into two groups. In Group A (single-layer), the disease distribution was as follows: caecal tuberculosis (n=3), carcinoma of the ascending colon (n=6), carcinoma of the caecum (n=2), caecal perforation due to trauma (n=4), carcinoma of the hepatic flexure (n=6), and others (n=2). In Group B (double-layer), there were 3 cases of caecal tuberculosis, 5 of carcinoma of the ascending colon, 5 of carcinoma of the caecum, 4 of caecal perforation due to trauma, 4 of carcinoma of the hepatic flexure, and 2 classified as others. When both groups were combined, carcinoma of the ascending colon was the most common diagnosis, observed in 11 patients (24%). Comparatively, carcinoma of the ascending colon and hepatic flexure was more frequent in Group A, whereas carcinoma of the caecum was more common in Group B.

Table 4. Duration of anastomosis in both groups

Duration of anastomosis (minutes)	Group A (Single-layer)	Group B (Double-layer)
10-15	1 (4%)	-
16-20	19 (83%)	-
21-25	3 (13%)	1 (4%)
26-30	-	17 (74%)
31-35	-	5 (22%)
Total	23 (100%)	23 (100%)

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Figure 16. Duration of anastomosis in both groups

In Group A (single-layer), the minimum time required to perform anastomosis was 10-15 minutes in 1 patient (4%), while the majority, 19 patients (83%), required 16-20 minutes; no anastomosis exceeded 25 minutes. In Group B (double-layer), the shortest duration was 21-25 minutes in 1 patient (4%), whereas most anastomoses, 17 patients (74%), were completed within 26-30 minutes; no procedure required more than 35 minutes. These findings indicate that single-layer anastomosis was consistently faster to perform than double-layer anastomosis.

Table 5. Comparison of mean duration of ileocolic end-to-end anastomosis in both groups

Groups	Mean ± SD (Duration in minutes)	T test	P value
Group A	18.43 ± 2.68	-13.314	<0.001
Group B	28.70 ± 2.55		

Figure 17. Comparison of mean duration of ileocolic anastomosis in both groups

The mean anastomotic time was significantly shorter in the single-layer group (18.43 ± 2.68 minutes) compared with the double-layer group (28.70 ± 2.55 minutes), demonstrating a mean difference of -10.26 minutes. This finding was highly statistically significant (p < 0.001), indicating that single-layer anastomosis can be performed in substantially less time than double-layer anastomosis without compromising surgical feasibility.

Table 6. Comparison of the outcomes in both groups

Outcomes		Group A (Single-layer)	Group B (Double-layer)	P value
Anastomotic leak	Yes	1 (4%)	2 (9%)	NS*
	No	22 (96%)	21 (91%)	
Surgical site infection	Yes	2 (9%)	2 (9%)	NS*
	No	21 (91%)	21 (91%)	
30-day mortality	Yes	0	0	NS*
	No	23 (100%)	23 (100%)	

*Not significant

In Group A (single-layer), an anastomotic leak was observed in 1 patient (4%), and surgical site infection occurred in 2 patients (9%); no 30-day mortality was reported. In Group B (double-layer), anastomotic leaks were noted in 2 patients (9%), surgical site infection in 2 patients (9%), and similarly, no 30-day mortality was observed. Comparative analysis between the two groups showed no statistically significant differences in the rates of anastomotic leak, surgical site infection, or 30-day mortality.

Table 7. Comparison of mean duration of hospital stay in both groups

Groups	Mean ± SD (Duration in days)	T test	P value
Group A	7.39 ± 0.50	-1.5	0.14
Group B	7.61 ± 0.50		

Figure 18. Comparison of mean duration of hospital stay in both groups

In this comparative study, the mean duration of hospital stay was 7.39 ± 0.50 days in Group A (single-layer) and 7.61 ± 0.50 days in Group B (double-layer). The mean difference between the two groups was -0.22 days. Statistical analysis using the unpaired t-test showed no significant difference (p

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> 0.05), indicating that the length of hospital stay was comparable between the two groups.

DISCUSSION

A single-center hospital-based interventional double-blinded randomized controlled trial was conducted in No. (1) Military Hospital (700 Bedded) to study and compare the clinical outcomes of single-layer and double-layer ileocolic anastomoses in patients undergoing right hemicolectomy. The trial included 46 patients who satisfied the selection and exclusion criteria. Of these, randomly, 23 patients underwent single-layer ileocolic anastomosis in right hemicolectomy, and 23 patients underwent double-layer ileocolic anastomosis.

All included patients in two groups were evaluated and compared by means of age and sex distribution, disease groups, duration of ileocolic anastomosis, postoperative outcomes (such as anastomotic leak, surgical site infection, and 30-day mortality), and postoperative hospital stay.

Anastomotic integrity remains one of the most important determinants of immediate postoperative outcomes in gastrointestinal surgery, as anastomotic failure significantly increases morbidity and mortality. The success of anastomotic healing depends largely on surgical technique, meticulous tissue handling, precise apposition of bowel ends, adequate blood supply, and absence of tension at the suture line. In addition, several systemic factors—including patient age, nutritional status, perioperative blood loss, use of corticosteroids, and the presence of comorbidities such as malignancy, diabetes mellitus, renal failure, jaundice, or history of radiation exposure—also influence healing (10).

Bowel anastomosis is frequently required in patients with intestinal malignancy, inflammatory bowel disease, infectious strictures such as intestinal tuberculosis, bowel obstruction, and certain congenital anomalies. The primary objective of anastomosis is to restore intestinal continuity after resection. Based on the involvement of intestinal layers, anastomoses are generally categorized as single-layer or double-layer techniques. Multiple studies have compared these two approaches, evaluating parameters such as operative time, patient compliance, complication rates, and overall safety (11).

In this study, 46 patients undergoing elective right hemicolectomy were included and divided into two groups: Group A (single-layer anastomosis) and Group B (double-layer anastomosis). Most patients were in the 41–60-year age group, accounting for 52.1% in Group A and 47.8% in Group B, consistent with previous literature indicating that right hemicolectomy is most performed in middle-aged patients. The double-layer technique was used more frequently in the 61–80-year age group, possibly reflecting surgeons' preference for a more "secure" anastomosis in patients with potentially fragile bowel tissue. In the very elderly (>80 years), only single-layer closure was employed.

With respect to sex distribution, 54.3% of the overall cohort were male and 45.6% female. Within groups, 56.5% of males underwent single-layer closure compared to 52.1% undergoing double-layer closure, whereas slightly more females underwent double-layer closure (47.8%) than single-layer closure (43.4%). These findings suggest that sex-based distribution was relatively balanced between techniques, and the choice of closure method may be influenced more by patient-specific and intraoperative factors than by sex.

The most common indication for right hemicolectomy was carcinoma of the ascending colon (23.9%), followed by carcinoma of the hepatic flexure (21.7%), caecal perforation (17.3%), carcinoma of the caecum (15.2%), and caecal tuberculosis (13%). The remaining 8.6% of patients fell into miscellaneous categories. This disease distribution aligns with previously published data and reflects the typical spectrum of pathologies requiring right hemicolectomy.

Intraoperative observations revealed that the single-layer anastomosis technique (Group A) required significantly less time compared to the double-layer technique (Group B). Most single-layer anastomoses (83%) were completed within 16–20 minutes, while double-layer anastomoses typically required 26–30 minutes (74% of cases), with some taking up to 31–35 minutes. The mean anastomotic time was significantly shorter in the single-layer group (18.43 ± 2.68 minutes) compared with the double-layer group (28.70 ± 2.55 minutes). The difference in mean anastomotic time was statistically highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This finding is consistent with previous studies reporting that single-layer techniques are faster, which may translate to shorter operative times and potentially reduce anesthetic exposure.

Postoperative outcomes were favorable in both groups. In Group A, the anastomotic leak rate was 4%, compared to 9% in Group B, though the difference was not statistically significant. Surgical site infections occurred in 9% of patients in both groups, and there were no 30-day mortalities. These findings are consistent with earlier systematic reviews and meta-analyses, which have shown no significant difference in leak rates or mortality between single- and double-layer techniques.

The overall complication rates in this study support the safety and efficacy of both techniques, but the slightly lower leak rate and reduced operative time observed with single-layer anastomosis suggest that it may be advantageous, particularly in patients where minimizing operative time is critical.

The mean length of hospital stay was 7.39 ± 0.5 days for the single-layer group and 7.61 ± 0.5 days for the double-layer group, with the difference being statistically insignificant. The double-layer group experienced a slightly longer stay, but this was likely clinically negligible and consistent with previous studies.

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This study demonstrated that both single-layer and double-layer anastomosis techniques provide comparable safety profiles, with no significant difference in anastomotic leak rates, surgical site infections, or 30-day mortality. However, single-layer anastomosis was associated with a significantly shorter operative time, making it an efficient option without compromising outcomes. These findings reinforce evidence from prior studies and meta-analyses suggesting that single-layer continuous anastomosis is not only safe and reliable but also time-saving, thereby potentially improving operative efficiency.

CONCLUSION

This study, involving 46 patients undergoing right hemicolectomy, demonstrated that single-layer continuous anastomosis required significantly less operative time than double-layer anastomosis without increasing the risk of postoperative complications such as surgical site infection, anastomotic leak, or 30-day mortality. Hospital stay was comparable between the two techniques. These findings support single-layer continuous anastomosis as a safe, efficient, and adoptable technique that can be reliably implemented in routine surgical practice.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of this study, single-layer continuous anastomosis should be preferred over the conventional double-layer technique in right hemicolectomy, as it significantly reduces operative time without increasing postoperative morbidity or mortality. Its simplicity, safety profile, and shorter learning curve make it a reliable option for routine surgical practice, particularly in resource-limited settings. Further large-scale, multicenter studies are recommended to validate these findings and establish standardized guidelines for its widespread adoption.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declared no potential conflict of interests with respect to authorship and publication of this article.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This randomized controlled trial was approved by the Hospital Research and Ethical Review Committee from No. (1) Military Hospital (700 Bedded), Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar. The period allowed by the Ethical Review Committee was from 01.12.2022 to 31.12.2024. The informed consent of human participants was obtained in written form.

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